

Plasmonic Metal Nanostructure Modified BiFeO₃ Heterostructured Photocatalyst for Visible Light Driven Photocatalytic H₂ Generation

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Abstract

Visible light active photocatalysts can offer a green approach to solve renewable energy production by solar light harvesting. In this regard, perovskite based oxide are considered as novel catalytic material for photochemical water splitting (1). However, the low charge separation efficiency and fast recombination rate lowers the catalytic efficiency (2). In this work, we overcome the aforementioned problems by decorating the ferroelectric BiFeO₃ (BFO) surface with plasmonic Au nanoparticles (NPs) to increase optical absorption in visible region. Herein, single crystalline BFO nanosheets (400 nm) have been successfully prepared by hydrothermal method and Au NPs (~ 17 nm diameter) have been introduced on the BFO hexagonal nanostructure via radiolysis process without using any toxic reducing agents. The as-synthesized materials have been used as the photocatalyst for hydrogen generation under visible light and the experimental result reveals that Au/BFO heterostructures are more efficient in water splitting compare to bare BFO nanosheets.

Keywords: Perovskites, Plasmonic metal nanoparticles, Heterostructures, Visible light active photocatalyst, H₂ generation

References:

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